

LIMONOIDS*

T. R. Govindachari

The role of acetic acid in the biosynthesis of complex natural products has become increasingly evident during recent years¹. Acetate can arise from fatty acid breakdown, as a product of carbohydrate metabolism and also from some amino acids. Acetate can also serve as a source of these substances and thus interconnect three major classes of natural substances, the fats, carbohydrates and proteins. Apart from this, a large number of natural products of diverse chemical types also seem to have acetate as the precursor. The major pathways are evident. One, through the self-condensation of acetate units to a polyketomethylene chain, which in turn cyclises to differing structures such as quinones, flavones, isoflavones, chromones, coumarins, xanthenes, benzophenones, depsides, etc. The other, through the sequence $\text{AcetylSCoA} \longrightarrow \text{AcetoacetylSCoA} \longrightarrow \text{Hydroxymethyl glutarylSCoA} \longrightarrow \text{Mevalonate} \longrightarrow \text{Isopentenylpyrophosphate} \longrightarrow \text{Polyisoprenoids}$. From the last, the vast number of mono-, di- and triterpenoids, the steroids and transformation products are derived.

It has been established that squalene is the precursor of lanosterol (I) which in turn is on the route to cholesterol from which the steroids are derived. The squalene chain can be folded in many ways leading to different triterpenes. Euphol (II), which differs from lanosterol only in having the enantiomeric configuration at the C/D ring junction and at C₁₇ can again be visualised as arising from squalene by a particular mode of following of the chain.

During recent years a large number of compounds have been investigated in the group of plant bitter principles, which seem to arise by the biosynthetic modification of the euphol structure. The most important of this is, of course, limonin, whose structure was unravelled by an international team of organic chemists

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1. J. H. Richards and J. B. Hendrickson, *The Biosynthesis of Terpenes, Steroids and Acetogenins*. W. A. Benjamin Inc., 1964.

and by X ray crystallography by Professor Robertson. A common feature in all these compounds is the loss of four carbon atoms from C_{24} to C_{27} and the cyclisation of C_{20} to C_{28} to form a furan ring. A β -monosubstituted furan ring is present in all these compounds. A second common feature is the migration of a methyl group from C_{14} to C_8 . A chemical analogy for this rearrangement would be the oxidation of dihydrobutyrospermyl acetate (III) to the ketone (IV). The presence of an oxygen function at C_7 in several compounds of this class is again significant.

Further modifications that take place are the introduction of oxygen function in one or other of the rings A to D, with or without concomitant bond cleavage in rings A to D. Examples of bond cleavage in each one of these rings are now known and I wish to deal in this lecture with selected examples. All these compounds can be grouped under the name 'limonoids'.

I should like to discuss in some detail the chemistry of cedrelone, obtained from the extracts of the wood of *Cedrela toona*^{a, b}. Cedrelone was first isolated by Parihar and Dutt⁴ in 1950, who assigned it the molecular formula $C_{25}H_{30}O_5$. Mass spectrometric investigation of cedrelone and several of its derivatives led to the revision of the formula to $C_{26}H_{30}O_5$. Two of the five oxygen atoms be located in a diosphenol system, as shown by the colour with ferric chloride, the spectral properties (λ_{max} 280 $m\mu$, ϵ 9100 shifted by base to 325 $m\mu$, ϵ 4250; IR bands at 3420, 1670 and 1610 cm^{-1}) and the preparation of a monoacetate and monomethyl ether. The NMR, spectrum of cedrelone disclosed the presence of (a) five tertiary methyl groups (1.56, 1.50, 1.29, 1.12, 0.75 δ), (b) a β -monosubstituted furan ring (7.36, 7.14 and 6.17 δ),

(c) an enone chromophore of the type
$$\begin{array}{c} \text{C} \\ | \\ \text{C}-\text{C} \begin{array}{l} \text{H} \quad \text{H} \\ \diagdown \quad \diagup \\ \text{C}=\text{C}-\text{C}=\text{O} \end{array} \\ | \\ \text{C} \end{array}$$
 (doublets at 6.9 and

6.1 δ , $J=10$ cps) and (d) an ether group of the type
$$\begin{array}{c} \text{C} \qquad \qquad \text{C} \\ | \qquad \qquad | \\ \text{C}-\text{C} \text{---} \text{O} \text{---} \text{C} \text{---} \text{H} \\ | \qquad \qquad | \\ \text{C} \qquad \qquad \text{C} \end{array}$$
 (3.78 δ).

2. K. W. Gopinath, T. R. Govindachari, P. C. Parthasarathy, N. Viswanathan, D. Arigoni and W. C. Wildman, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 446.
3. (a) I. G. Grant, J. A. Hamilton, T. A. Hamor, R. Hodges, S. G. McGeachin, R. A. Raphael, J. M. Robertson and G. A. Sim, *ibid.*, 1961, 444 ;
(b) R. Hodges, J. G. McGeachin and R. A. Raphael, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 2515.
4. D. B. Parihar and S. Dutt, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 27, 77.

Confirmation of the presence of a furan ring was furnished by a positive Ehrlich test. Mild catalytic hydrogenation of cedrelone gave a dihydro derivative (λ_{\max} 280 $m\mu$, ϵ 8050; IR bands at 1700 and 1680 cm^{-1}) which was also obtained by treatment with sodium borohydride at room temperature. Base-catalysed addition of methanol gave a methoxy derivative (λ_{\max} 280 $m\mu$, ϵ 8050; IR bands at 1710, 1675 cm^{-1}) and oxidation in alkaline hydrogen peroxide gave an epoxide (λ_{\max} 275 $m\mu$, 9700; IR bands 1710, 1670 cm^{-1}).

Hydrogenation of cedrelone or dihydrocedrelone in presence of a more active Palladium/Carbon catalyst gave hexahydrocedrelone (λ_{\max} 382 $m\mu$, ϵ 9200; IR bands 3440, 1710, 1675, 1610 cm^{-1}) in which the diosphenol system is still retained. Since neither this compound nor its acetate contains a vinyl hydrogen (NMR), the diosphenol double bond must carry two β -substituents. Treatment of cedrelone acetate with BF_3 yields isocedrelone acetate, which has a free hydroxyl group. This may be taken as evidence for the presence of an epoxy ring in cedrelone.

The C_{26} formula, the presence of a β -monosubstituted furan ring were reminiscent of limonin. By assuming that cedrelone arises from the same precursor euphol, structure (V) can be proposed. Further evidence supporting this structure

was also obtained. Treatment of cedrelone with boiling 10% methanolic potassium hydroxide gave isocedrelonic acid (VI), $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_8$, characterised as the methyl ester (λ_{\max} 235 $m\mu$ log ϵ , 18,500; IR bands 3450, 1715, 1660 cm^{-1}). The NMR spectrum of this compound indicates the presence of the eneone chromophore. The presence of a vinyl furan was indicated by the positive test with tetranitromethane and the appearance of a new chromophore (λ_{\max} 242 $m\mu$, log ϵ , 13500 from the subtraction curve) and the shift to lower fields of the furan protons. Formation of this acid involves the benzylic acid rearrangement of the diosphenol group and the opening of the epoxide ring with migration of a methyl group from C_{13} to C_{14} . It has been shown by Raphael et al.^{3b} that the epoxide ring opening takes place at the time of acidification and not before. The driving force may be the strain inherent in the boat-shaped ring C with two trans-fused five-membered rings attached to it.

Treatment of cedrelone acetate with boron trifluoride gave isocedrelone acetate (VII) in which again a vinyl furan chromophore is present as shown by the appearance

of a new chromophore (subtraction curve λ_{\max} 242 m μ , log ϵ 13200). The structure of cedrelone has been derived independently by X-ray crystallography⁵. Various

VII.

gradations in oxidation states of the modified euphol framework can be discerned in grandifolione⁶ (VIII), gedunin⁷ (IX), anthothecal⁸ (X) and hirtin⁹ (XI).

VIII

IX

X

XI

A number of compounds are known in which in addition to the transformations observed in compounds of the type of cedrelone, further modifications have taken place by way of cleavage of one or other of the carbocyclic rings. Among compounds in which both A and D rings have been cleaved, the most important example is limonin¹⁰ (XII) and the related compounds citrolin¹¹ (XIII), nomilin¹² (XIV) and obacunone¹³ (XV).

5. I. G. Grant, J. A. Hamilton, T. A. Hamor, J. M. Robertson and G. Sim, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 2506.
6. J. D. Connolly, K. L. Handa, R. McCrindle and K. H. Overton, *Chem. Commun.*, 1967, 867.
7. J. Akisanya, C. W. L. Bevan, T. G. Halsall, J. W. Powell and D. A. H. Taylor, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 3705; S. A. Sutherland, G. A. Sim and J. M. Robertson, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1961.
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9. W. R. Chan and D. R. Taylor, *Chem. Commun.*, 1966, 206.
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11. O. H. Emerson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 545; 1952, 74, 688.
12. O. H. Emerson, *ibid.*, 1951, 73, 2621.
13. T. Ramikawa and T. Kabota, *Tetrahedron*, 1961, 12, 262; T. Matsuura, T. Kamikawa and T. Kubota, *ibid.*, 1961, 12, 269; T. Kubota, T. Matsuura, T. Tokoroyama and T. Matsumoto, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1961, 10, 325.

An interesting compound belonging to this group is veprisone, a neutral crystalline compound isolated from *Vepris bilocularis*. This was shown to be methyl

XII

XIII

XIV

XV

epiisobacunoate¹⁴ (XVI) earlier reported as an amorphous solid and obtained through a sequence of degradations from obacunone (XV).

There are several examples known in which in addition to the general modifications of the euphol structure such as the fission of the C₁₇ side chain and migration

XVI

XVII

XVIII

of the methyl at C₁₄ to C₈, ring B has been cleaved. Some examples are andirobin¹⁵ (XVII), methyl angolensate¹⁶ (XVIII), mexicanolide¹⁷ (XIX), swietenine¹⁸ (XX), fassinolide¹⁹ (XXI), etc.

14. T. R. Govindachari, B. S. Joshi and V. N. Sundararajan, *Tetrahedron*, 1964, 20, 2985.
15. W. D. Ollis, A. D. Ward and R. Zelnik, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1964, 2607.
16. C. W. L. Bcyan, J. W. Powell, D. A. H. Taylor, P. Toft, M. Welford, W. R. Chan, B. S. Mootoo and T. G. Halsall, *Chem. and Ind.*, 1964, 1751.
17. J. D. Connolly, R. McCrindle and K. H. Overton; *Chem. Commun.*, 1965, 162.
18. J. D. Connolly, R. Henderson, R. McCrindle, K. H. Overton and N. S. Bhacca, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1964, 2593.
19. R. Zelnik and C. M. Rosito, *ibid.*, 1966, 6441.

Maxicanolide, for instance, can be visualised as arising from the modification of the euphol structure to the intermediate (XXII), by rotation of the $C_{10}-C_9$ bond, followed by Michael addition of the active methylene at C_2 to C_{10} .

Yet another modification of the euphol system is seen in nimbin²⁰ (XXIII) and salanin²¹ (XXIV), the important feature being the cleavage of ring C. A plausible biogenetic pathway has been suggested for nimbin, involving the hypothetical intermediate (XXV).

Many more compounds than those mentioned in this lecture have been isolated during the past few years which apparently arise from structural modification of

20. C. R. Narayanan, R. V. Pachapurkar, S. K. Pradhan, V. R. Shah and N. S. Narasimhan, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1964, 2, 108.

21. R. Henderson, R. McCrindle, K. H. Overton and A. Melera, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1964, 3969.

XXIII

XXIV

XXV

euphol. NMR spectroscopy has played an important role in the elucidation of structures of these compounds. One cannot fail to be struck by the fact how these highly complex structures are derived by a few simple oxidations on the euphol framework.

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